

THEORETICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODERN PROJECT OF THE AIRPORT BUILDING

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the prospects for the organization of local government at a new level as a result of localization of advanced foreign experience, national values in order to achieve the full goals of reforms in the developing new Uzbekistan, to ensure the welfare of the state and society.

Airports, as a rule, are considered a large public facility of universal importance, which, as a rule, express the first impression about the city, and sometimes about the whole country; such conditions affect the special (specific) requirements that they are imposed on architectural compositions.

Like other public buildings, airport solutions are also split into centralized, blocked and pavilions schemes. Compact solutions of separate monofunctional airport buildings are characteristic for centralized airports. Airports that are united or cooperative with other buildings (with administrative, technical and other buildings) are among the blocked airports.

Modern principles of Organization of the internal environment significantly affect the volumetric and planned structure of airports. Traditional luxury buildings are replaced by light, laconic-shaped pavilion buildings. Instead of outdated traditions such as filling the airport with relatively small rooms and lounge lanes, changes are being made to large rooms that allow passengers to move freely, as well

as technological schemes that firstly has adopted by replacing equipment.

Constructive schemes of airports with different capacities and purposes are also diverse. In the practice of the country, regional-column reinforced concrete structures are widely used, which can be an example of reinforced concrete structures with base sets of 6x6, 6x12 and 6x18 m, while using prefabricated industrial materials.

Despite this, even in some rare constructions, standard (tipovoy) prefabricated constructions can be successfully applied. For example, in the airport of the city of Moscow, as well as in the airports of Moscow-Vnukovo and Moscow-Sheremetyevo, the passenger halls are closed by Standard (tipovoy) reinforced concrete farms, the range of which is 18 m.

Modern foreign practice itself is characterized by a wide variety of constructive schemes. With axial-column constructions and systems, double-sided curved coatings and other spatial constructions are also used. In addition to these, traditional wood, plaster,

wood and natural stone materials of different texture are successfully used.

Sometimes in the OMS of the yams there are wooden gluing regions (the Airports of Harlow and Coventry in Great Britain. The airport in Vancouver, Canada), shuttles in the form of paraboloids (an airport in the Dutch city of Rotterdam), Open metal wire Farms (an airport in the French city of Rene) are served.¹

Vant constructions have a special perspective, reducing the weight of the closing and at the same time leading to the fact that the intermediate distance by extending is limited by the minimum number of supports.

The entire outer walls of the building are closed with 32 metal balcony closures, which are continuous, console hangers (Naves) on the perimeter (range 35 m). The height of the ceiling above the apron closure is 15 m. This, in turn, allows the introduction of the largest aircraft under the hood and the protection of passengers and servicemen from precipitation. The airport closure is a fairly large ellipse with dimensions of 120 m and 160 m according to the arrows on the plan.

The comfort level of the modern airport is determined by the most used technological and engineering equipment, escalators and moving pavements, cargo carriers and lifting devices, telescopic traps, sun protection overhead blinds, automatic opening doors, etc.

The highest artistic and aesthetic efficiency can be achieved only by a mutually suitable solution of all buildings, structures and elements that are included in the airport complex.

In the process of transition from transport to transport, passengers can use not only Apron hangers (naves), but also common rooms. Since the movement of the shuttle on

the field is common, the routes of movement of the passenger should be short and safe.

The proportions of different types of vehicles can be different. But it is necessary to adhere to the principle of sequence in the unity and interaction of the organizers of each passenger connecting nodes.

The standards of airport design always stipulate the placement of a certain number of hotels (most first of all, for transit passengers), as well as public catering facilities that occupy a significant area in major airports.

Often airports are cooperated with institutions that provide commercial services. An example of this is the auto-Airport in Chikago (this complex also houses 18 shops), the airports in Osaka and Hamburg (cooperated with shopping centers), the commercial passage Street, which is combined with the largest Post Office Central Airport in Brussels (Figure 1).

Modern civil aviation has airports that are far away from the city, most of which are connected by Highways. For this reason, in the last years, direct urban service to farmers has been developing.

Transport agencies of the city and the city do not differ from the airports only by location. If airport are connected with airplanes, then the airports will depend only on buses, cars, sometimes railroads, subway and other destination delivery lines.

¹ Turayev X. A. et al. *METHODICAL RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE THEME OF FORTY*

IN DRAWING LESSONS GRAPHICALLY //Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 264-268.

Figure 1

Co-operation with the cultural and domestic service institutions of Railway, bus and other airports is also economically effective. It is known that the construction and capture of one large building will be less than the total cost of going to several small buildings built in different areas of the same size.²

The norms that assess the basic architectural and compositional solution of airports include the following:

1. The presence of a principled architectural and spatial scheme, the shape (configuration) and basic dimensions of a specially designed complex, as well as the construction and natural coverage of an

existing or projected City, the space between the different airports and the airport, the maintenance of the passenger buildings (one or more) and the basic elements of the apron to provide a mutually.

2. The operations that all the main rooms conduct are sequentially arranged in accordance with the character and the schedule (schedule) of movement of passengers (passengers) of different categories.

3. Ensuring a composite integrity (the mass of, suitability, proportionality of parts), as well as the compatibility of the image description (characteristic) and the content of the conducted with the tectonic scheme of the airport complex, the interaction of the main hall groups and other rooms.

4. Ensuring that the scale or dimension of vehicles (scale) and human scale, architectural composition of small form, beautification and landscaping, technical aesthetic elements and monumental (decorative) are mutually proportional with the application of intermediate elements of the projected image.

In the future, a principled new means of communication can be created, for example, the train tracks moving in air or magnetic pads, the planes that fly faster than the speed of sound, as well as standing-up, etc.

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